
The Impact Compensation Management Strategies to Job Stability Applying to Sample of Sudanese Banks

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1. ABSTRACT

This study aims to explore the impact of compensation management strategies on job stability in Sudanese banks in the state of Khartoum. Centred on the question of how compensation strategies contribute to enhancing employee stability, by analysing components such as salary levels, pay structures, allowances, benefits, and their ability to retain employees. The researchers adopted a descriptive analytical approach, relying on a questionnaire as the primary tool for collecting data from a sample of 130 employees working in banks operating in Khartoum State. Data were analysed using appropriate statistical software such as SPSS, and various tests were applied, including Alpha Cronbach, linear regression, and the T-test. The results revealed a statistically significant relationship between compensation management strategies and job stability. The findings indicated that salaries and financial benefits significantly influence an employee's decision to remain stable in their job. The findings showed the most prominent of which is that there is no positive statistically significant relationship at the level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) between the salary level and the dimensions of job stability, and there is a statistically significant relationship at the level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) between the additions to salaries and the dimensions of job stability. A statistical significant relationship at the level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) between advantages, benefits and dimensions of job stability was revealed. The study concluded that implementing an effective compensation strategy positively contributes to enhancing employee stability. It recommended improving salary structures and offering additional benefits to promote workforce retention.

Keyword: Compensation management strategy, Job stability, Job engagement, Functional homology.

2. INTRODUCTION

In the era of global competition, compensation management strategies have become very important for employee retention and job stability, as many companies and organizations compete in employee compensation methods and provide the best and most rewarding compensation strategies for their employees. This is because it has become one of the competitive advantages that companies and organizations compete for in providing the best compensation offers to attract and retain competent employees and ensure their job stability within the organization. (By **researcher**).

Employees are the organization's key resource and they account for either success or failure of organization whether public or private. The ability of the employers to attract, retain, and reward their staff is therefore, an important challenge of contemporary organizations. Hence, the need to retain employees especially the talented and competent ones with motivating compensation packages. The willingness of employees to remain with an organization largely depends on compensation packages of the organization. Therefore an organization that is desirous of ensuring employees optimal performances and that employee remain with it, needs to consider a variety of appropriate ways to

reward the employees to get the desired results It has been argued that the degree to which employees are satisfied with their jobs and their readiness to remain with an organization is a function of compensation packages and reward system of the Organization.(**SamuelVictorAkpan1| Ayandele Isaac Ayayinka2 | Obialor, Donatus Chukwuemeka – 2022**).

Compensation Management is an important element of the company's management. In return for work performed, compensation is a systematic method to provide workers monetary value. Compensation may contribute to recruiting, working performance and job satisfaction for many reasons. Managers must recognize the significance of competitive pay and their human resources and an effective investment outlook on salaries. For an enterprise, maintaining wage levels that attract and retain high-quality personnel is essential while recognizing the need to control payroll expenses.

(**N.SIREESHA, D.SWAPNA, D.NIROSHA- 2019**).

In today's ever-evolving job market, job stability can feel like an elusive goal. With advances in technology, shifting global economies, and changes in how businesses operate, the traditional idea of working at one company for decades is becoming less common. As I reflect on what job, stability means in the modern workforce, it is clear that both individuals and companies need to rethink their approach to careers and employment security. (By **researcher**)

In the recent past, the question of job security and the stability of employment relationships has been increasingly discussed. The general notion is that job stability is on the decline in most OECD countries, although the actual empirical evidence is scarce and ambiguous. Several studies for Germany and other OECD countries like the United States, the United Kingdom and France show some limited evidence of increasing job instability.

One major reason for some economists to be concerned about declines in job stability is the potential effect on individual career paths. Too many job switches and periods of unemployment may lead to losses in human capital, decreasing earnings potentials, and a limited capability to obtain work due to disadvantageous signals (Spence, 1973). Furthermore, economy-wide long-term labor relationships might be one prerequisite for a highly educated workforce (Acemoglu and Pischke, 1998), which is, in turn, amongst other things, responsible for economic success.

(**Annette Bergemann- 2004**). In this research, we will study the impact of compensation strategies followed by private or public organizations on job stability and the extent of their contribution to employee security and stability. (By **researcher**).

Hence, the research problem emerged as the following main question: How does the compensation strategy contribute positively to the job stability of employees?

From which the following sub-questions emerged:

- 1- To what extent is there a statistically significant relationship between the age of the salary level and the job stability of employees?
- 2- What is the level of the relationship between the salary structure and the job stability of employees?
- 3- Is there a statistically significant relationship between salary additions and the job stability of employees?

Is there a statistically significant relationship between benefits and the job stability of employees?

The main objective of this study is to understand the compensation strategy and its impact on job stability in Khartoum State by identifying the relationship between the dimensions of the compensation strategy represented in the level of salaries, salary structure, salary additions, benefits, and the ability to retain employees and make them more stable.

There are other sub-objectives, the most important of which are:

- 1- Knowing the degree of relationship between the level of salaries and the job stability of employees.
- 2- Identifying the level of relationship between the salary structure and the job stability of employees.
- 3- Discovering the relationship between salary additions and the job stability of employees.
- 4- Determining the relationship between benefits and the job stability of employees.

Study limitations:

- Time frame: The study was conducted between 2021-2022.
- Spatial boundaries: Sudan - Khartoum State.
- Human borders: managers - department heads - employees in commercial and government banks in Khartoum State.

Conceptual boundaries: The study was limited to the concept of compensation management and the concept of job stability

3. RELATED LITERATURE

3.1 Compensation Strategy

Compensation management remains one of the most complex and dynamic challenges in human resource management (Barry et al., 1995). It plays a critical role in aligning individual and organizational goals, thus influencing motivation, productivity, and employee retention. Compensation is broadly defined as all forms of financial and non-financial returns provided by employers in exchange for employee services (Sireesha, Swapna, & Nirosha, 2020). It is both a strategic tool and a motivational driver that connects employer and employee, serving as a basis for fostering performance and commitment (Obianuju, Emejulu, & Nwanneka, 2017; Samuel-Victor-Akpan, Ayandele, & Obialor, 2022).

A well-structured compensation strategy addresses multiple objectives including attracting talent, motivating personnel, optimizing costs, and ensuring internal and external consistency in remuneration (Sharma, Garg, & Bansal, 2020). Strategic compensation systems help organizations develop competitive advantage by aligning pay practices with market benchmarks and performance expectations.

3.2 Types of Compensation

Compensation strategies can be broadly categorized into financial and non-financial components (Aliu, Osanebi, & Adeoue, 2024). Financial compensation includes direct payments such as salaries, wages, and bonuses, as well as indirect benefits like health insurance, retirement packages, and allowances. These incentives are commonly linked to organizational goals and individual performance metrics.

Conversely, non-financial compensation involves recognition, responsibility, autonomy, skill development, and career advancement opportunities. Such rewards, although intangible, are pivotal in building intrinsic motivation and enhancing job satisfaction (Aliu et al., 2024). They foster psychological attachment and reinforce commitment, especially in knowledge-intensive or service-oriented sectors.

3.3 Dimensions of Compensation Strategy

This study emphasizes four dimensions of compensation strategy relevant to organizational performance and employee engagement:

- **Salary Structure:** A framework that defines pay ranges for different roles based on internal equity and external competitiveness (SHRM, 2024).
- **Salary Level:** The actual monetary value paid to employees, which reflects the organization's compensation philosophy (CIPD, 2023).
- **Salary Additions:** Variable elements such as bonuses, commissions, and overtime, tied to individual or collective performance (SHRM, 2024).
- **Benefits and Advantages:** These include non-cash benefits like insurance and retirement plans, contributing to employee well-being and organizational loyalty (CIPD, 2023).

3.4 Job Stability

Job stability, defined as the duration of the employee–employer relationship, is a vital determinant of organizational performance and individual well-being (Valletta, 1999; Borland, 2000). While stability provides employees with security and predictability, excessive rigidity may hinder growth and innovation.

Recent literature highlights heterogeneity in job stability across labor markets. Some individuals hold long-term positions, while others experience intermittent employment (Kuhn & Ploj, 2020). These differences have significant implications at both micro and macroeconomic levels, influencing career progression, organizational continuity, and societal welfare.

3.5 Dimensions of Job Stability

Building on recent frameworks, this study identifies the following dimensions of job stability:

- **Functional Connection:** Reflects emotional and mental engagement of employees with their organization, motivating high effort and commitment (Al-Madi & Al-Shanfi, 2021).
- **Functional Symmetry:** Represents the degree to which employees adopt organizational values and norms, facilitating alignment with corporate culture (Hanan, 2018).
- **Job Commitment:** Involves employees' desire to remain with the organization and contribute positively to its goals.
- **Emotional Commitment:** Indicates employee satisfaction with the organizational environment and their role in decision-making processes.
- **Normative Commitment:** Reflects a moral obligation to stay, often influenced by organizational support and inclusive planning.
- **Continuous Commitment:** Describes a cost–benefit evaluation of remaining with the organization, based on potential gains or losses from switching employment.
- **Social Integration:** Acknowledges the human desire for connection and the impact of workplace relationships on employee satisfaction (Al-Washai & Al-Washai, 2020).

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 HIERARCHY OF NEEDS THEORY :

"Social needs" or "esteem", "[self-actualization](#)" and "[transcendence](#)" to describe the pattern through which human needs and motivations generally move. According to the theory, this means that for motivation to arise at the next stage, an individual must satisfy each prior stage. The hierarchy has been

used to explain how effort and motivation are correlated in the context of [human behavior](#). Each of these individual levels contains a certain amount of internal sensation that must be met in order for an individual to complete their hierarchy. The goal in Maslow's hierarchy is to attain the level or stage of self-actualization.

Although widely used and researched, Maslow's hierarchy of needs lacks conclusive supporting evidence and the validity of the theory remains contested in academia. One criticism of the original theory, which has been revised into newer versions of the theory, was that the original hierarchy states that a lower level must be completely satisfied and fulfilled before moving onto a higher pursuit; there is evidence to suggest that levels continuously overlap each other.

(Wikipedia website)

Maslow's hierarchy of needs

Fig.1

4.2 STUDY MODEL:

The model shows the impact of compensation management strategy as an independent variable, the dimensions of which are (salary level, salary addition, benefits and advantages, salary structure) and its impact on job stability as a dependent variable, the dimensions of which are (job attachment, job similarity) as the subject of the study. (By researcher):

Fig .2 STUDY MODEL

4.3 Study hypotheses:

Based on the logical relationships shown by the study model, and then formulate the main study hypotheses.

The sub-branch is as follows:

4.3.1 The first main hypothesis:

There is a statistically significant relationship at the level of between ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) compensation management strategy and dimensions of job stability.

The following sub-hypotheses branch out from the first main hypothesis:

- 1- There is a statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) between the level of salaries and the dimensions of job stability.
- 2- There is a statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) between the salary structure and the dimensions of job stability.
- 3- There is a statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) between salary additions and the dimension of job stability.
- 4- There is a statistically significant relationship at the level of ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) between the advantages, benefits, and dimensions of job stability.

4.3.2 Second main hypothesis:

There is a statistically significant relationship at the level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) for practicing the dimensions of compensation management strategy: salary level, salary structure, salary additions, benefits and advantages in enhancing the degree of job stability.

4.3.3 The third main hypothesis:

There are statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) between the average responses of the respondents regarding the practice of compensation management strategy attributed to the demographic variables (gender, age, educational level Position, number of years of experience).

4.3.4 The fourth main hypothesis:

There are statistically significant differences at the ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) level between the averages of respondents' opinions about the personal and functional compensation management strategy (gender, age, educational level, job, number of Years of experience).

4.4 Reliability

Table1: Accreditation

	Variables	Matches	Cronbach's alpha
independent variable	Salary level	5	0.85
	Salary additions	5	0.84
	Advantages and Benefits	4	0.74
Dependent variable	Functional connection	7	0.88
	Functional symmetry	3	0.67

	Professional compatibility	2	0.65
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Source: Prepared by researchers from field study data 2022

To ensure the degree of reliability, the questionnaire questions were tested based on the reliability scale. The table shows that the Cornbrash's alpha reliability coefficient was highly reliable, as the reliability coefficient for the statements that make up the independent variables reached (0.85), salary additions (0.85), benefits and advantages (0.74). The table also shows the reliability coefficient for the statements that make up the dependent variables: job attachment (0.88), job similarity (0.67), and professional compatibility (0.65).

Fig 3. Modified Study Mode

4.4.1 Main hypothesis

There is a positive relationship between compensation strategy and job stability.

4.4.2 Sub-hypotheses

1. Salary level affects job engagement.
2. Salary additions affect job engagement.
3. Advantages and benefits affect job engagement.
4. Salary level affects job matching.
5. Salary additions affect job matching.
6. Advantages and benefits affect functional symmetry.
7. Salary level affects career compatibility.
8. Salary additions affect professional compatibility.
9. Advantages and benefits affect professional compatibility.

4.4.3 Hypothesis Testing:

1. Testing the relationship between the components of compensation strategy and job stability:

The following table shows the regression coefficient of compensation strategy and job stability (Beta coefficient). Multiple regression analysis test was used to identify the effect of the strategic dimensions. Compensation for functional association). The (Beta) coefficient was relied upon to know the expected change in the variable.

The dependent variable is due to the change in one unit of the independent variable. (R) was also relied upon to identify the model's ability to explain the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable, in addition to using the F-test.

Identifying the significance of the regression model.

The significance level of 0.05 was relied upon to judge the extent of significance. Impact, where the calculated significance level was compared with the value of the adopted significance level, and the effects are considered significant. Statistic if the value of the calculated significance level is less than the approved significance level (0.05) and vice versa true, and through regression analysis it was concluded that there is no positive relationship between the level of salaries and functional correlation reached (0.019) level of significance (0.777), while there is a relationship between the additions on salaries and job engagement, where it reached (0.268) at the significance level (0.000) "and there is a relationship between the mirror, benefits and functional association reached between (0.313) and the significance level (0.000) as shown in table during.

Table2: The relationship between the dimensions of compensation strategy and job engagement:

independent variable	Job affiliation	Sig
Salary level	.019	0.000
Salary additions	.268	0.000
Advantages and Benefits	.313	0.000
R ²	.241	
Adjusted R ²	.233***	
Variable R ²	.241	
F change	29.408	

Note: Level of significant: *p<0.10, **p<0.05, ***p<0

Source: Prepared by researchers from field study data (2012).

2. Testing the relationship between the components of compensation strategy and job stability:

The following table shows the regression components of compensation strategy and job stability (Beta coefficient). A multiple regression analysis test was used, which aims to identify the effect of the dimensions of compensation strategy on job homogeneity. The (Beta) coefficient was relied upon to know the expected change in the dependent variable due to the change in one unit of the independent variable. (R) was also relied upon to identify the model's ability to explain the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable, in addition to using the F test to identify the significance of the regression model. The significance level of 0.05 was relied upon to judge the extent of the significance of the effect, as the calculated significance level was compared with the value of the adopted significance level. The effects are considered statistically significant if the value of the calculated significance level is smaller than the adopted significance level (0.05) and vice versa. Through regression analysis, it was concluded that there is no positive relationship between the salary level and functional symmetry, as Beta (0.069) reached the significance level (0.355), and there is no relationship between salary additions and functional symmetry, as Beta (0.117) reached the significance level (0.124), while there is a relationship between mirrors and functional symmetry benefits, as Beta (0.234) reached the significance level (0.001), as shown in the table Sons.

Table 3: The relationship between the dimensions of compensation strategy and job symmetry:

independent variable	Functional symmetry	Sig
Level up	.069	0.355
Addition to salaries	.117	0.124
Advantages and Benefits	.234	0.001
R ²	.076	
Adjusted R ²	.066**	
Variable R ²	.076	
F change	7.623	

Note: Level of significant: *p<0.10. *p<0.05.p

Source: Prepared by researchers from field study data (2022)

3. Testing the relationship between the components of compensation strategy and job stability:

The following table shows the regression components of compensation strategy and job stability (Beta coefficient). A multiple regression analysis test was used, which aims to identify the effect of the dimensions of compensation strategy on job compatibility. The (Beta) coefficient was relied upon to know the expected change in the dependent variable due to the change in one unit of the independent variable. (R) was also relied upon to identify the model's ability to explain the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable, in addition to using the F test to identify the

significance of the regression model. The significance level of 0.05 was relied upon to judge the extent of the significance of the effect, as the calculated significance level was compared with the value of the adopted significance level. The effects are considered statistically significant if the value of the calculated significance level is smaller than the adopted significance level (0.05) and vice versa. Through regression analysis, it was concluded that there is a positive relationship between the level of salaries and professional compatibility, as Beta (0.139) reached the significance level (0.026), and there is a relationship between salary additions and professional compatibility, as Beta (0.312) reached the significance level (0.000). There is also a relationship between benefits and professional compatibility, as Beta (0.259) reached the significance level (0.000).

As shown in the table below

Table 4: The relationship between the dimensions of compensation strategy and job engagement:

independent variable	Professional compatibility	Sig
Salary level	.139	0.026
Addition to salaries	.312	0.000
Advantages and Benefits	.259	0.000
R²	.347	
Adjusted R²	.340***	
Variable R²	.347	
F change	49.172	

Source: Prepared by researchers from field study data (2022)

Table 5: Testing the first hypothesis:

There is a positive relationship between compensation strategy and job stability - Partially supported.	Proof case
Salary level affects job engagement	Did not support
Salary additions affect job engagement.	Fully supported
Advantages and benefits affect job engagement	Fully supported
Salary level affects job matching.	Did not support
Salary additions affect job matching.	Did not support
Advantages and benefits affect functional symmetry.	Supported
Salary level affects career compatibility.	Supported
Salary additions affect professional compatibility.	Fully supported
Advantages and Benefits Affect Career Compatibility	Fully supported

Source: Prepared by researchers from field study data (2022).

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter contains a general summary of the most important results extracted from this study, then a discussion of the results of the study with the results of previous studies in terms of difference and agreement, followed by the effects of the theoretical and applied study, in addition to presenting a set of recommendations and a set of proposals for future research, then we conclude with a summary and conclusion of the study.

The study results indicated the following:

- 1- There is no statistically significant positive relationship at the level of ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) between the level of salaries and the dimensions of job stability.
- 2- There is a statistically significant relationship at the level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) between salary additions and dimensions Job stability.

- 4- There is a statistically significant relationship at the level ($\alpha \geq 0.05$) between the advantages and benefits and the dimensions of stability Career.

5.1 Results Discussion:

The relationship between salary levels and job stability dimensions: This hypothesis tested salary level, dimensions and job stability, and it was found that there is no statistically significant positive relationship between salary level, dimensions and job stability, as salary level does not play a major role in job attachment or job similarity, and therefore there is a statistically significant relationship but with a negative direction, which partially negates the presented null hypothesis. This is largely consistent with the findings of Sharahili's study (2020), which demonstrated that there is a feeling of dissatisfaction on the part of employees with the basic salary, and also consistent with Aayomiolarew's study (2019), which concluded that there was a weak association between reward management and worker motivation. It was also revealed that in the insurance industry in Nigeria, compensation management has a weak effect on worker motivation, as well as Azam's study (2019), which failed.

The study reported a significant impact of rank on the opportunity and nature of the job: This hypothesis tested the relationship between salary additions and job stability dimensions, and it was found that there is a completely positive relationship between salary additions and job stability dimensions, as Salary additions play a positive role in job stability. This is largely consistent with the findings of the study (Sharahili (2020) which demonstrated that there is a feeling of dissatisfaction among employees with the rewards they receive for the work they do, in addition to the distribution of rewards, as they believe that rewards are often not distributed to those who deserve them. It also agreed with the study (Marwan (2018) which concluded that there is a strong relationship between the compensation system and improving the quality of educational services. The research led to raising the quality of educational services and making improvements to salaries so that the employee does not have to work for another source of livelihood.

The relationship between salary additions and job stability dimensions: This hypothesis tested the relationship between benefits and dimensions of job stability, and it was found that there is a completely positive relationship between benefits and dimensions of job stability, as the more benefits and advantages an employee has, the higher his job stability rate. This is largely consistent with the findings of the Eugookang (2021) study, which demonstrated that there is a significant statistical relationship between employee competencies and organizational culture. These findings can be supported by current research indicating that compensation plans were associated with multiple types of organizational competence and different organizational cultures, and it is consistent with the Azzam (2019) study, which found a significant and positive impact of life balance Process, satisfaction, benefits of structural capital and talent retention.

The relationship between benefits and dimensions of job stability: This hypothesis tested the relationship between benefits and dimensions of job stability, and it was found that there is a completely positive relationship between benefits and dimensions of job stability, as the more benefits and advantages an employee has, the higher his job stability rate. This is largely consistent with the findings of the Eugookang (2021) study, which demonstrated that there is a significant statistical relationship between employee competencies and organizational culture. These findings can be supported by current research indicating that compensation plans were associated with multiple types of organizational competence and different organizational cultures, and it is consistent with the Azzam

(2019) study, which found a significant and positive impact of life balance Process, satisfaction, benefits of structural capital and talent retention.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS.

- **In light of the results of the study, the following recommendations can be made:**

1. Ensure that the salary level in this bank is consistent with what is prevalent in the labor market.
2. Ensure that bank management raises salaries annually by certain percentages that are commensurate with the requirements of living.
3. The bank management must establish a wage structure that is fair both internally and externally.
4. The bank's management should provide fair benefit packages as provided by the management of other banks.
5. The level of knowledge of the gifted must be taken into consideration.
6. I am proud to belong to the bank I work for.
7. The bank's interest in appreciating the work done by employees.

- **Suggestions for future research :**

In light of the study results, the researchers suggest a set of future studies that can be conducted in a manner related to the subject under study, as follows:

1. Study the compensation system in human resources and its impact on achieving the organization's goals.
2. Study the role of compensation strategies in achieving competitive advantage.
3. Study the effect of the moderating role of intellectual capital on the relationship between compensation strategies and performance.
4. Study the impact of compensation strategies on promoting employee performance.
5. Study the impact of human resources management on employees' job stability and organizational culture as a moderating role

7. CONCLUSION

The term compensation is often used by employers to refer indirectly and comprehensively to salaries, while in reality compensation includes more than just the employee's basic salary; this term refers to the basic salary, health insurance provided by the company to employees, and any bonus or additional benefits such as transportation allowance, annual travel tickets, or any tuition fees provided by the company to employees' children. Compensation strategies are not only aimed at attracting talent to your company, but also at retaining current talent for as long as possible; when your current employees feel that you care about rewarding and providing them with awards, their level of motivation will increase, which will push them to work harder, and thus contribute to the success of your company more. Since the success of organizations depends on their human energies (individuals), which are a source of strategic competitive advantage and achieving goals, it is necessary to invest in employees and feed and care for them. Therefore, human resources are considered one of the most important elements in the organization.

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